

Lung cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the training and validation of AI models

ID: bae8fdcb-1bca-46b6-9c58-56071de64473

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/bae8fdcb-1bca-46b6-9c58-56071de64473/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 1088

Subjects count: 1088

Age range: Between 29 years and 91 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, LUNG, NECK, HEAD, BRAIN, WHOLEBODY, THORAX INJECTE, THORAX, THORAX / ABDOMEN, TAP, SPINE, TORAX, TAP IV, TOTAL BODY, HEART, COU THORAX, TB COLLO, TC TOTAL BODY, CTAP, ABDOPELV, SINUS CTAP, TDM ABDOMEN / PE, THORAX IV, ABDO PELVIS, CRANE, THORAX CRANE, SERVICE, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT